

COMPARATIVE EFFICACY OF BIORATIONAL AND CHEMICAL INSECTICIDES AGAINST CITRUS LEAF MINER

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Abstract

The field experiment was conducted to evaluation of biorational component and chemicals for the management of citrus leaf miner in nursery during September – October of 2014 at Centre of Excellence for Citrus, Bharat Nagar, Horticulture Section, College of Agriculture, Nagpur (Dr. PDKV, Akola). The Trail was laid out in randomized block design with nine treatments and three replications. All recommended packages and practices were followed to raise the nursery plant. The results were found to be statistically significant. The significantly lowest leaves infestation of leaf miner was recorded in Abamectin 1.8 EC (6.10 per cent). It was most significant over all the treatments and was at par with Spinosad 45 SC which recorded (7.18 per cent) leaves infestation. However, the next effective treatments Acetamiprid 20 SP and Imidacloprid 17.8 SL which recorded 9.34 and 10.31 per cent leaves infestation. The remaining treatments viz. Neem oil 2%, NSE 5%, *Beauveria bassiana* 1x10⁸ CFU/ml and *Metarhizium anisopliae* 1x10⁸ CFU/ml determined 14.83, 15.23 and 16.75 per cent leaves infestation of citrus leaf miner, respectively.

Key Word: Citrus, Leaf miner, Biorational component and chemical insecticides.

Introduction

Citrus fruit production is the third largest fruit industry in the country, which has a considerable importance in the economy of the country. Citrus fruit are rich in vitamin C, minerals and alkaline salts. It is also good source of vit. A and B, fruit sugars, fruits acid, Calcium, Phosphorus and Iron. In India area under citrus fruit crop is about 1034 hectare and its production is 13200 metric tons.. (Anonymous, 2018) Citrus leaf miner, *Phyllocnistis citrella*, is a small lepidopteron pest of citrus. Damage is caused by the larvae as they mine immature foliage. Twisted and curled leaves are generally the first symptoms noticed. Severe infestations (average of two or more mines per leaf) can retard the growth and yield of nursery and newly planted trees, but their effect on mature trees is less serious. It has about 5-9 generations in a year, with peak periods in early summer and early autumn. It has high migration ability from outside of orchards and high fertility. It present in epidermis of citrus leaf and get substantial protection, therefore it get difficult to direct contact of chemical to the larval body. Commonly used insecticides are not able to manage the infestation of leaf miner in nursery. Therefore it is very important to evaluate the biopesticides as well as insecticides against citrus leaf miner. In Vidarbha Citrus leaf miner is a serious pest in nursery and field condition. Its infestation in spring, monsoon and autumn season was observed as high as 54.7 per cent, 52 per cent and 43.4 per cent respectively. (Shivankar and Rao, 2003). Predation and parasitism action of bio agents was also increased simultaneously but it could not get successful control. Because citrus leaf miner infestation build up from nursery and it reaches to the main orchard, therefore quality and quantity of citrus fruit is deteriorate. Thus, it is most essential to manage citrus pests in nursery and provide pest free seedlings to the farmers and also check the further development of infestation in main field. Hence it is necessary to identify such biopesticides and insecticides which are having good potential to manage nursery pests in all stage of citrus crop. Therefore, under present investigation, it was planned and selected, such biopesticides and insecticides which have broad spectrum activity for managing nursery pest citrus leaf miner.

Material And Methods

The study was carried out in the month of September-October 2014 at Centre of Excellence for Citrus (Indo- Israel Project), Bharat Nagar, Horticulture Section, College of Agriculture, Nagpur with a view to evaluate their efficacy of biorational and chemical insecticides for the management of citrus leaf miner under nursery on Nagpur mandarin grafts. The experiment was conducted in randomized block design with nine treatments and three replications. Variety select for experiment was Nagpur mandarin. All recommended packages and practices were

followed to raise the nursery plant. The investigation was conducted with impose of treatments, T₁ -*Beauveria bassiana* @ 1x10⁸ CFU/ml, T₂ -*Metarhizium anisopliae* @ 1x10⁸ CFU/ml, T₃ -NSE @ 5 %, T₄ -Neem oil @ 2 % , T₅ Spinosad 45 SC, T₆ -Imidacloprid 17.8 SL, T₇ -Acetamiprid 20 SP, T₈ -Abamectin -1.9 EC, T₉ -Control (water spray)

Method of recording observation

1. Pre-treatment observations were taken at before 24 hours of treatment application. Post-treatment observations were taken at of 3 and 7 days after treatment application.
2. Total 4 spraying were given at 10 days interval during the course of investigation.
3. Counted total leaves and damage leaves by citrus leaf miner on 5 randomly selected plants from each treatment block for recording of percent leaf miner infestation.
4. Counted live and dead larvae of citrus leaf miner on infested leaves at pre treatment and post treatment period on five randomly selected plants from each treatment block for recording percent mortality.
5. The data generated in respect of per cent infestation of nursery pest on citrus were transformed into arc sin and square root value as per Gomez and Gomez, (1984) and then subjected to statistical analysis to test the level of significance of treatment.

Results and Discussion

Present study was conducted for evaluation of biorational and chemical insecticides for the management of leaf miner on citrus under shade net nursery on grafts of Nagpur Mandarin at Center of Excellence for Citrus (Indo-Israel Project) Bharat Nagar, College of Agriculture, Nagpur during 2014-2015.

Cumulative effect of fourth application on per cent infestation of citrus leaf miner in nursery at 3 DAS

The data presented in Table 1 indicated that all the treatments were significantly superior over control (water spray) in recording of minimum per cent leaf infestation of citrus leaf miner in nursery. From the cumulative data of third day after spraying of all four applications revealed that Abamectin 1.8 EC (6.43%) was significantly superior over all the treatments and found at par with Spinosad 45 SC which recorded (8.05%) per cent of leaf miner infestation. Whereas, Acetamiprid 20 SP and Imidacloprid 17.8 SL recorded 10.15 and 10.94 per cent infestations of leaf miner was next in order of merit and found significantly superior to Neem oil, NSE, *Beauveria bassiana* 1x10⁸ CFU/ml and *Metarhizium anisopliae* 1x10⁸ CFU/ml recorded 14.10, 14.47, 16.44 and 17.58 per cent leaves infestation of citrus leaf miner, respectively. Maximum per cent leaves infestation i.e. 25.14% was noticed in Control (water spray). Lad et al. (2006) and Perovic et al.

(2006) studied the efficacy of insecticide against citrus leaf miner under field condition and reported that Imidacloprid 0.005% was better than other insecticide in controlling of citrus leaf miner. Regarding Acetamiprid, Mungroo and Abeeluck (1999), Zang *et al.* (2001), Cai Zijian *et al.* (2007) and Harendra Singh Saravanan (2008) showed significant results against citrus leaf miner.

B. Cumulative effect of four applications on per cent infestation of citrus leaf miner in nursery at 7 DAS

Analysis data presented in Table 2 on per cent citrus leaf infestation after seven days after spraying of revealed that minimum leaf infestation due to citrus leaf miner was recorded in treatment Abamectin 1.8 EC (5.78 per cent leaves infestation) and was most significant over all the treatments. Same kind of result was obtained in treatment Spinosad 45 SC as it was second in order of merit recording 6.32% leaves infestation and found significantly superior to Acetamiprid 20 SP, Imidacloprid 17.8 SL, *Beauveria bassiana* 1×10^8 CFU/ml, Neem oil, *Metarhizium anisopliae* 1×10^8 CFU/ml and NSE in which 8.54, 9.68, 14.99, 15.57, 15.93 and 16.00 per cent leaves infestation recorded, respectively. Significantly highest per cent leaves infestation i.e. 25.14 % was noticed in Control (water spray). Similar findings are also recorded by Salas *et al.* (2006) when they treated Imidacloprid 35 SC @0.105 g a.i. per plant against citrus leaf miner exhibited lowest per cent leaf miner infestation than other treatments. Similar results were also showed by Raga *et al.* (2001), Perovic *et al.* (2006), Salas *et al.* (2006), and Sharma and Bhatti (2012) and they reported that these treatments were effective in reducing leaf miner infestation at 7 DAS. Abamectin 1.8 EC showed at par result with Thiamethoxam 25 WP. While Acetamiprid 20 SP and Spinosad 45 SC recorded as second effective treatment followed by Diflubenzuron 25 WP.

C. Overall, cumulative effect of four applications on per cent infestation of citrus leaf miner in nursery

The data presented in Table 3 indicated that all the treatments were significantly superior over control. The minimum per cent leaves infestation was observed in the treatment Abamectin 1.8 EC i.e. 6.10 per cent and found significantly superior over others. The next best treatment was Spinosad 45 SC, which showed 7.18 per cent infestation of leaf miner and was significantly superior to Acetamiprid 20 SP and Imidacloprid 17.8 SL which recorded 9.34%, 10.31% of leaf miner and these were at par with each other. Third effective group of treatments viz. Neem oil, NSE, *Beauveria bassiana* 1×10^8 CFU/ml and *Metarhizium anisopliae* 1×10^8 CFU/ml which recorded 14.83, 15.23, 15.71 and 16.75 per cent leaves infestation of citrus leaf miner, respectively. The highest infestation was noticed in treatment Control (water spray) i.e. 25.14 per cent. In present study Abamectin, Spinosad and Acetamiprid showed the minimum per cent leaves infestation. Similar findings were also reported by Perovic *et al.* (2006), Rao *et al.* (2008). In the investigation of Su Wen Wei (2000), Urrutia and Gonzalez (2003) and Rao *et al.* (2008), they reported that Abamectin 1.8 EC found to be better than all the treatments in reduction of citrus leaf miner infestation. Hence findings of these treatments are in agreement with the result of present experiment and support the data. Zang Quan Bing *et al.* (2001) reported that Acetamiprid was effective for leaf miner control. Similar findings were also reviewed by Perovic and Hrcin (2008), Mungroo and Abeeluck (1999), Herendra Singh Saravanan (2008). These findings of workers are comparable with our findings, and gave support to the data.

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Table No.3 Overall Cumulative effect of four applications on per cent infestation of citrus leaf miner in nursery

Sr. No.	Treatments	Conc. (%)	(%) Leaves infestation at		(%) Mean Leaves infestation
			3 DAS	7 DAS	
1	<i>Beauveria bassiana</i>	1x10 ⁸ CFU/ml,	16.44 (23.90)	14.99 (22.76)	15.71 (23.34)
2	<i>Metarhizium anisopliae</i>	1x10 ⁸ CFU/ml,	17.58 (24.79)	15.93 (23.51)	16.75 (24.15)
3	NSE	5.0	14.47 (22.36)	16.00 (23.57)	15.23 (22.96)
4	Neem oil	2.0	14.10 (22.05)	15.57 (23.23)	14.83 (22.64)
5	Spinosad 45 SC	0.03	8.05 (16.39)	6.32 (14.48)	7.18 (15.52)
6	Imidacloprid 17.8 SL	0.005	10.94 (19.31)	9.68 (18.13)	10.31 (18.72)
7	Acetamiprid 20 SP	0.04	10.15 (18.56)	8.54 (16.98)	9.34 (17.78)
8	Abamectin 1.8 EC	0.003	6.43 (14.34)	5.78 (13.64)	6.10 (14.30)
9	Control (water spray)		25.14 (30.09)	25.14 (30.09)	25.14 (30.09)
	'F' Test		Sig.	Sig.	Sign.
	SE (m) ±		0.72	0.69	0.663
	CD @ 5 %		2.11	2.03	1.882

(Figures in parentheses are corresponding values of arc sin transformation.)

Table 1: Effect of biorational component and molecules of insecticides on per cent infestation of citrus leaf miner after 3 DAS.

Sr. No.	Treatments	Conc. (%)	(%) Leaves infestation at 3 DAS				Mean
			I spray	II spray	III spray	IV spray	
1	<i>Beauveria bassiana</i>	1x108 CFU/ml,	16.75 (24.16)	17.99 (25.10)	16.58 (24.03)	14.42 (22.32)	16.44 (23.90)
2	<i>Metarhizium anisopliae</i>	1x108 CFU/ml,	17.15 (24.46)	18.67 (25.60)	17.74 (24.91)	16.76 (24.17)	17.58 (24.79)
3	NSE	5 %	14.05 (22.01)	14.45 (22.34)	15.22 (22.96)	14.16 (22.10)	14.47 (22.36)
4	Neem oil	2.0	13.69 (21.72)	15.10 (22.87)	14.51 (22.39)	13.10 (21.22)	14.10 (22.05)
5	Spinosad 45 SC	0.03	9.96 (18.40)	9.24 (17.70)	7.34 (15.72)	5.64 (13.74)	8.05 (16.39)
6	Imidacloprid 17.8 SL	0.005	11.04 (19.41)	10.92 (19.30)	11.50 (19.82)	10.30 (18.72)	10.94 (19.31)
7	Acetamiprid 20 SP	0.04	11.17 (19.52)	8.76 (17.22)	10.40 (18.81)	10.27 (18.69)	10.15 (18.56)
8	Abamectin 1.8 EC	0.003	10.26 (18.68)	7.68 (16.09)	4.68 (12.49)	3.08 (10.11)	6.43 (14.34)
9	Control (water spray)		24.32 (29.55)	25.17 (30.11)	25.04 (30.03)	26.02 (30.67)	25.14 (30.09)
	'F' Test		Sign.	Sign.	Sign.	Sign.	Sig.
	SE (m) ±		0.746	0.679	0.647	0.713	0.72
	CD @ 5 %		2.237	2.036	1.939	2.138	2.11

(Figures in parentheses are corresponding values of arc sin transformation.)

Table 2: Effect of biorational component and molecules of insecticides on per cent infestation of citrus leaf miner after 7 DAS.

Sr. No.	Treatments	Conc. (%)	(%) Leaves infestation at 7 DAS				Mean
			I spray	II spray	III spray	IV spray	
1	<i>Beauveria bassiana</i>	1x108 CFU/ml,	14.97 (22.76)	16.86 (24.24)	14.46 (22.35)	13.68 (21.71)	14.99 (22.76)
2	<i>Metarhizium anisopliae</i>	1x108 CFU/ml,	16.90 (24.27)	16.88 (24.25)	14.88 (22.69)	15.06 (22.84)	15.93 (23.51)
3	NSE	5 %	15.34 (23.06)	16.61 (24.05)	15.60 (23.26)	16.42 (23.91)	16.00 (23.57)
4	Neem oil	2.0	14.84 (22.66)	16.99 (24.34)	15.60 (23.26)	14.85 (22.66)	15.57 (23.23)
5	Spinosad 45 SC	0.03	7.38 (15.77)	7.25 (15.62)	6.44 (14.70)	4.21 (11.84)	6.32 (14.48)
6	Imidacloprid 17.8 SL	0.005	9.70 (18.15)	9.90 (18.33)	9.39 (17.84)	9.74 (18.18)	9.68 (18.13)
7	Acetamiprid 20 SP	0.04	8.78 (17.24)	7.25 (15.62)	9.17 (17.63)	8.95 (17.41)	8.54 (16.98)
8	Abamectin 1.8 EC	0.003	9.83 (18.27)	5.73 (13.86)	3.83 (11.28)	3.73 (11.14)	5.78 (13.64)
9	Control (water spray)		23.32 (28.88)	26.17 (30.77)	25.04 (30.03)	26.02 (30.67)	25.14 (30.09)
	'F' Test		Sign.	Sign.	Sign.	Sign.	Sig.
	SE (m) ±		0.733	0.650	0.719	0.721	0.69
	CD @ 5 %		2.196	1.948	2.155	2.160	2.03

(Figures in parentheses are corresponding values of arc sin transformation.)